

Meta-Analysis of Marketing Innovation on Firm's Performance of Small & Medium Enterprises With the Moderating Effect of Government Support Program: In Case of Selected Sub-cities of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

Fisseha Dejene Yadete¹, Shashi Kant², Chalchissa Amentie Kero³

¹PhD Scholar, Department of Marketing Management, College of Business & Economics, Bule Hora University, Ethiopia.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Management, College of Business & Economics, Bule Hora University, Ethiopia.

³Associate Professor, Department of Management, Jimma University, Ethiopia.

Abstract – This study looked at how market innovation affected SMEs' performance in Addis Abeba, Ethiopia, with the use of government support programmes as a moderator. The study's meta-analysis will be guided by the Schumpeter innovation theory, which also incorporates the diffusion of innovation theory, expectancy theory, institutional theory, stakeholder theory, absorptive capacity theory, resource-based view/theory, dynamic capability theory, R-A theory, and unified theory of acceptance and use of technology. The researcher used an effect size approach based on a forest and funnel plot to scan, exclude, and include relevant material. Researchers discovered a connection between the Dimension of Innovation and company performance on the basis of an extensive literature review. Also Based on the studied literature, the researcher discovered a link between the moderation of the government support programme and the performance of SMEs' firms in the area of innovation. To carry out this study, an exploratory sequential mixed research design will be used. Based on the current literature, the study attempts to create a conceptual framework and testable hypotheses. It was discovered that the impact of marketing innovation on a firm's performance was moderated by government support programmes. Businesses must be encouraged to adopt government support programmes with a moderating influence as a result.

Keywords: Marketing Innovation, Forest Plot, Funnel Plot, Meta Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

The relationship between SMEs' company performance, the innovation dimension, and government support programmes: Since these factors give the businesses a sustainable competitive advantage based on an orientation towards their market and an improvement in their capacity to respond to customer needs, marketing innovation enables businesses to improve their market share and increase their capacity for growth (Daksa et al., 2018). The ability to develop methods, techniques, and ideas for work that help in improving the circumstances of the work field (Adula & Kant, 2022) as well as the motivation of employees and the development of their skills and talents to achieve the highest levels of productivity goals and performance are all examples of organisational innovation (Kiende, Mukulu, & Odhiambo, 2019).

Improvement in product design, location, promotion, or pricing is referred to as marketing innovation (Wakjira & Kant, 2022). Empirical studies have sought to demonstrate the potential links between marketing innovation and SME business success. Market-driven innovations work by enhancing current products and

services to better meet consumer needs (Peng et al., 2021). The results of the study by Cuevas-Vargas et al. (2021) indicate that there is a statistically significant association between marketing innovation and business performance through GSP. This relationship is tempered by the adoption of ICT as a GSP component.

The relationship between radical innovation and firm performance has been moderated by environmental factors, according to research by Ibrahim and Yusheng in 2020 and D. S. Wang in 2019b. Government support has a more significant influence as a moderator between the environment context and the adoption of technological innovation, where the relationship is positive. In addition, they discover that external factors have little influence on the relationship between incremental innovation and company performance, which has a detrimental effect on the strategies for incremental innovation. Because there were no archives with the specific data needed to assess firm performance and innovation, a survey method was used.

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Innovation affects how well a firm performs, and if appropriately supported by government assistance programmes, it leads to improved firm performance. This is due to the fact that there are always forces for inclusion and forces for exclusion in each proposal for government support programmes (Abbasnejad & Norouzi, 2021). The impact of innovation on company success, however, has been the subject of previous empirical research, some of which are included below.

The SMEs in Ethiopia have poor levels of innovation in the small and micro-enterprise sector, according to the studies listed below. For instance, the research by Talegeta (2014) and Gobena & Kant (2022) showed that there are several impediments to innovation, such as a shortage of trained workers, insufficient R&D, business size, and excessive expenses of innovation spending. In a similar vein, (Kassa & Getnet Mirete, 2022) found that government backing, access to infrastructure, owner leadership, entrepreneurial training, and entrepreneurial mentality all had an impact on the creativity of micro and small businesses engaged in service and manufacturing. According to another researcher, the size of the company and its access to financing have a considerable impact on how innovative the micro and small businesses in Ethiopia are (Ayinaddis, 2022).

According to the study's findings, the leadership of the owners, access to infrastructure, entrepreneurial training, entrepreneurial mentality, and government assistance all had a major impact on how innovative service and manufacturing MSEs were (Bansal & Kant, 2018.). The performance of Mozambique SMEs' exports is positively impacted by their innovation skills (Moreira & Navaia, 2022). Using sustainable strategies including green HRM, a green supply chain, green innovation, and green marketing, Alraja et al. (2022) discovered a substantial correlation between technical innovation and sustainable performance. According to Adam & Alarifi (2021b), SMEs' innovation methods have a substantial impact on their performance and ability to survive, and it is crucial to have external support to further enhance this impact. Government Support significantly improved SME performance and attenuated the association between IC and SME performance in a favourable way (Otache & Usang, 2021).

The performance of manufacturing SMEs is positively and significantly impacted by marketing innovation. Both organisational innovation and innovation culture have a significant and advantageous effect on business performance. The study's findings indicated that product innovation had a favourable impact on consumer interest (Sinaga et al., 2021). According to this study, there is an association between the

performance of SMEs and SI (strategic innovation). They discovered a robust, positive association between government funding for innovation techniques and the performance of SMEs (Adam & Alarifi, 2021). The performance of SMEs is strongly correlated with each of the characteristics (Bansal & Kant, 2018.). Government assistance plays a larger role as a moderator between the acceptance of technical innovation in the context of the environment, where there is a positive relationship, and the rate of change.

On the other hand, research has shown that both market-driven and market-driving innovations have a major impact on a firm's performance. The level of competition and the state of technology considerably mitigate their effects. Variables relating to innovations and financial performance have a negative correlation (Peng et al., 2021). Using time-series data, according to (Edeh et al., 2020). First, we discover that while process innovation boosts export performance, product innovation has a detrimental effect. On the other hand, marketing innovation had a negligible and minor impact. A firm's performance, both financially and non-financially, is not considerably impacted by aggregate innovation. Only the marketing innovation of the four dimensions of innovation has a substantial impact on the financial and non-financial success of the company (Mabenge et al., 2023). The true impact and significance of marketing innovation for manufacturing organisations is not presented (Del Carpio Gallegos & Miralles, 2020).

Researchers found that no Universal theory was used in previous studied literature. Different researchers used different theoretical base to access the relationship between variables. Some also tried to combine the related theories to magnify the effect. Likewise Schumpeter theory (1942) was used by (Bahta et al., 2021; Daksa et al., 2018; Dushime et al., 2021; Feng et al., 2020; KAU, 2021; Xin et al., 2022). Studies by (S. M. Chege et al., 2020a; KAU, 2021; Ngisau & Ibrahim, 2020; Purwati & Hamzah, 2021) was based on Diffusion of innovation (DOI) theory (1962). Research by (Canh et al., 2019; Chopra, 2019; Jiang et al., 2019; KAU, 2021; Lee, 2019) was depend on Expectancy Theory (1964). On the basis of the researches by (Ademe, 2020; Institutional, 2019; Xie, Qi, et al., 2019) was based on Institutional Theory (late 1970). Other studies were depending on (Awa & Igwe, 2017a; Deelert, 2020; Deelert et al., 2022; Ghaleb et al., 2021).

3. SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- Marketing innovation has statistically significant relationship with firm performance.
- Government support program has moderate effect between marketing innovation and firm performance.

4. EMPIRICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

Table -1: Systematic literature review on Marketing Innovation and Firm Performance

No	Author(s), Study Area	Objective of the study	Methodology	Research findings:	Limitation /Research Gap
1	(Peng et al., 2021): China	To analyze the dimensions of marketing innovations, their effects on firm performance, and how market environmental factors moderate those effects	The authors collected primary data from 352 enterprise managers in China from September 2018 to October 2019. Hierarchical regression analysis was conducted to examine the main effects of marketing innovation and the moderating effect of market environmental factors.	Results show that both market driven and market-driving innovations significantly contribute to a firm's performance. Moreover, their effects are significantly moderated by competition intensity and technological turbulence but not demand uncertainty.	-The analysis utilized cross-sectional data and so cannot verify the findings at different time points. -This study measured research variables with managers' perceptions. -The data of this study were collected from a wide spectrum of industries in China; the generalizability of the findings can be further validated in other economies.
2	(Cuevas-Vargas et al., 2021): Mexico	To analyze the effects of the adoption of ICTs on marketing innovation as a key strategy to increase the business performance	Research Methodology: The study used descriptive design and a quantitative approach using the sample of 228 SMEs and statistical technique known as (PLS-SEM).	Marketing innovation has a positive and significant effect on the performance of manufacturing SMEs. - Adoption of ICTs moderated the marketing innovation and business performance.	The study has limitation of using only quantitative approach.
3	(Hussain et al., 2020): Pakistan	To understand the relationship among marketing innovation and market performance in the hotel/restaurant industry.	Primary data collecting from a defined sample of a population. A deductive research approach was incorporated in this study, which is related to positivist philosophy. The study adopted a quantitative research approach only.	The results show that sustainable marketing assets marketing innovation have positive and significant effects on market performance.	-There is an issue in generalizing the findings of the current study to all customers of the whole. -Only quantitative research approach.

4	(Del Carpio Gallegos & Miralles, 2020)	To analyze how external sources of market knowledge, product innovation, and organizational innovation are related to marketing innovation.	Data collected from National Innovation Survey of the Manufacturing Industry were used. The measurement model was estimated using Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA),	Marketing innovation does not present its real impact and importance for manufacturing companies.	Limitation is that the study sample included different industries.
5	(Adamu et al., 2020): Nigeria	To determining the linkages between innovative marketing approaches and efficiency of small business in the furniture industry.	The study adopted a quantitative approach. Sample size of 203 respondents was chosen employees' relational using Yamane (1965) formula.	Marketing innovation strategies positively impact on SMEs efficiency. All the variables show a strong relationship with SMEs performance.	The study adopted a quantitative approach only. Small sample size
6	(Medrano et al., 2020)	To explore the relationship between companies' marketing innovation and environmental orientation and to determine how this relationship differs between manufacturing and service companies.	The study uses secondary data from the Technological Innovation Panel (PITEC) to look at 6,435 Spanish companies during the 2013–2015 period. To examine the contingency effect of the activity sector, the sample is divided into two subsamples: manufacturing companies and service companies. Partial least squares path modeling is used to test and validate the research model and proposed hypotheses.	The results show there is a statistically significant negative relationship between marketing innovation and environmental orientation. Significant differences were also found between manufacturing and service companies depending on the companies' activity sector and size.	This study has some limitations, such as the use of a secondary database only.
7	Muharam et al., (2020): Indonesian	To investigate the moderating role of disruptive technology on the relationship of process innovation and market innovation with Indonesian	Research design is a method of gathering and analyzing data to arrive at a solution. The approach adopted in this research is cross-sectional and applies the quantitative approach that is based on deductive reasoning.	The result of the study is a positive relationship between process innovation, market innovation and financial performance of firms. While, disruptive technology	In this study the researcher did not indicate about the limitation of the study. But the researcher used quantitative approach only.

		pharmaceutical firms' financial performance.		moderates the relationship of process.	
8	(Udriyah et al., 2019):Malaysia	To determine the effects of market orientation and innovation toward competitive advantage and business performance of textile SMEs in Selangor, Malaysia.	The sample size is 150.The primary type of data used in this research is quantitative data.	Market orientation and innovation partially have positive effects on the competitive advantage.	The limitation of the study is less sample size and used quantitative approach only. Other limitation in this study comes from resources, such as time, energy, and costs.

Source: Researchers own literature review (2023)

5. META ANALYSIS OF REVIEWED LITERATURE

Table -2: Effect Size

Study name	Partial Correlation	Partial Correlation (z)	Number of observations	Weight %
Peng et al., 2021	0.36	0.38	352.00	6.30%
Cuevas-Vargas et al., 2021	0.78	1.05	230.00	8.88%
Hussain et al., 2020	0.64	0.75	180.00	1.84%
Del Carpio Gallegos & Miralles, 2020	0.68	0.82	200.00	19.95%
Adamu et al., 2020	0.65	0.77	203.00	18.96%
Medrano et al., 2020	0.65	0.77	384.00	23.77%
Udriyah et al., 2019	0.69	0.84	203.00	20.30%

Source: Meta Essentials (2023)

Fig -1: Forest Plot
Source: Meta Essentials (2023)

Researchers by above forest plot discovered through met analysis that the top of the plot's x-axis represents the effect size scale of the examined systematic literature. Except for the bottom row, each row shows the estimated effect size from a reviewed systematic study as a point and (95%) confidence interval. The results of a single study were presented in this statistically accurate manner as an estimate of the interval in which the "actual" effect (of the studied systematic literature) was most likely to lie. Every study included in the meta-analysis was thought to be a study of a complete probability sample of a particular population, according to researchers. A smaller or larger bullet in the forest plot corresponds to the point estimate. A smaller or larger bullet in the forest plot corresponds to the point estimate. The proportional size of these bullets indicates how important a study was in producing the meta-analytic outcome.

Fig -2: Regression of Moderator on Correlation
Source: Meta Essentials (2023)

Table -3: Intercept Moderation

	B	SE	CI LL	CI UL	β	Z-value	p-value
Intercept	0.85	0.74	-1.52	3.21		1.14	0.254
Moderator	0.00	0.05	-0.15	0.14	-0.27	-0.07	0.947

Source: Meta Essentials (2023)

Researchers discovered that the moderator of the government support programme is a third variable that influences the relationships between the other two. Since the relationships between two variables are represented by their effect sizes, any variable that predicts the effect sizes is a moderator. The significance of the interaction term was the main consideration for the researcher when evaluating the findings of a moderation analysis. The moderator Government support programme has a considerable moderating effect on the relationship between market innovation and business performance, according to research that found the interaction term's effect on the endogenous construct to be significant.

Table -4: Variance of the True Effect Sizes

Combined effect size	0.80
T ² (method of moments estimation)	0.00
R ²	7.55%

Source: Meta Essentials (2023)

T² was significant, and the researchers used this information to estimate the variance of the real impact sizes. While computing the variance of these effects, researchers assumed that "if we had an indefinitely large sample of studies, each itself infinitely big (such that the estimate in each study equaled the genuine effect), this variance would be τ^2 ." In our meta-analysis, the between-study variation is 2. It is an estimation of the genuine effect sizes' underlying distribution's variance. As the chart above demonstrates, there are several suggested methods to calculate τ^2 .

6. PUBLICATION BIAS ANALYSIS

According to researchers, an area of study's body of research is likely to be prejudiced in many different ways. The likelihood that a statistically significant result will be published is predicted to be higher than that of a statistically non-significant result. As a result, the study's estimated cumulative effect size may be higher than it actually is. The examination of publication bias aims to (1) alert the reader to this potential publication bias and (2) correct the estimate for the total effect magnitude.

Fig -3: Funnel Plot

Source: Meta Essentials (2023)

Six distinct analyses that used by the researchers to point to publication bias are provided by Meta-Essentials. A funnel plot is a type of analysis. It is believed that observed effect sizes should be more or less symmetrically distributed around the total effect size when measured with similar precision (i.e., with similar standard error). As was already indicated, it is predicted that outcomes farther from the null will outnumber those closer to it. The figure above shows that this is not the case. According to the Trim-and-Fill approach, there are no imputed data points, hence the funnel plot shows there is no asymmetry in the distribution of effect sizes. However, the Trim-and-Fill strategy would impute one or more studies and afterwards modify the overall effect size for the potentially missing studies if we found asymmetry.

Table -5: Egger Regression

Egger Regression				
	Estimate	SE	CI LL	CI UL
Intercept	-0.74	1.29	-3.90	2.42
Slope	0.69	0.06	0.54	0.83

Source: Meta Essentials (2023)

The researchers employed the Egger's regression test to quantitatively evaluate this disparity. It looks at the correlation between the measured effect sizes and their sample standard errors (SEs); a large correlation shows the presence of effects from small studies. With a p-value of 0.775, Egger's test for a regression intercept revealed no indication of publication bias. Funnel plot suggests that there may be publishing bias. The rank correlation test by Begg and Mazumdar produced a p-value of 0.091, suggesting potential publication bias.

Table -6: Heterogeneity

Heterogeneity	
Q	12.16
p_Q	0.058
I^2	50.66%
T^2	0.00
T	0.05

Source: Meta Essentials (2023)

The researchers observed that considerable heterogeneity ranged from 50% to 90%. When there is substantial statistical heterogeneity, it means that the studies are not all estimating the same quantity. However, this does not necessarily imply that the true intervention effect varies. Significant statistical heterogeneity was arisen from methodological diversity or differences in outcome assessments.

Fig -4: Standardized Residual Histogram

Source: Meta Essentials (2023)

The Standardized Residual Histogram is based on the researchers' hypothesis that a normal distribution should be expected to surround the combined effect size for the z-scores of different studies, also known as standardised residuals. Researchers binned the residuals and plotted them against an expected normal distribution to see whether there are any outliers in the effect sizes. The proportion of residuals in each of the nine bins, which are used to organise the standardised residuals, determines the height of the bar (see above Figure).

Fig -5: Galbraith Plot

Source: Meta Essentials (2023)

To produce the Galbraith plot or radial plot, researchers must first conduct an unweighted regression of z-scores on the inverse of the standard error with the intercept restricted to zero (Galbraith, 1988). (see Figure 24). To find outliers in the effect sizes, use this figure. The two (lighter coloured) confidence interval lines are expected to contain 95% of the studies' results. A map, a table with regression estimates, and a table containing studies are all provided by MetaEssentials.

Table -7: Regression estimate

Regression estimate				
	Estimate	SE	CI LL	CI UL
Intercept	0.00			
Slope	0.66	0.02	0.62	0.70

Source: Meta Essentials (2023)

Researchers have also employed normal quantile plots, often known as Q-Q plots, to determine whether data are normally distributed. The researchers anticipated that all data points would be roughly on a straight line, indicating that the data would be dispersed according to a conventional normal distribution. A table comprising studies, a graphic, regression estimates, and an input option for calculating sample quantiles make up this component of Meta-Essentials. The calculated normal quantile, sample quantile, and research names are shown in the table. These normal and sample quantiles are shown on the plot along with a regression line. The user has the choice to base the sample quantiles on "Standardized residuals" or "Z-scores" using the input option.

Fig -6: Normal Quantile Plot
Source: Meta Essentials (2023)

Table -8: Regression estimate

Regression estimate				
	Estimate	SE	CI LL	CI UL
Intercept	12.74	0.86	10.64	14.84
Slope	7.73	1.02	5.23	10.23

Source: Meta Essentials (2023)

7. FAILSAFE-N TESTS

Many estimates of the Failsafe figures are included in the Publication Bias Analysis sheet's last section. To demonstrate this, researchers will pretend that a number of other papers are never published for any given study. Suppose that the results of these extra studies are negligible, or that their impact sizes are close to zero. The failsafe number then calculates the approximate number of such extra studies needed to make the combined effect size from the included and additional studies inconsequential, or nearly zero.

Table -9: Failsafe tests

Failsafe tests	
Rosenthal	
Overall Z-score	33.71
Failsafe-N	2934
Ad-hoc rule	Counterfeit

Source: Meta Essentials (2023)

8. CONCLUSION

To assess the (weighted) average effect size, the dispersion of effect sizes, the homogeneity (or heterogeneity) of the entire set of observed effect sizes and of subgroups, and to explore the applicability of possible moderators, researchers performed meta-analysis. The degree of heterogeneity should be evaluated and analysed before any judgements are made. Only when there is no question about the homogeneity of a group or subgroup of observed effect sizes may "combined" effect sizes be used as an outcome, and even then, only for the domain that is defined by this particular group of populations. The main outcome of most meta-analyses is an understanding of the dispersion of genuine effects because relevant heterogeneity is typically discovered by the researchers in this study. Meta-analysis serves as a tool for developing theories concerning "moderators" of the effect under those circumstances. Meta-analysis shouldn't be utilised for "testing" or for making generalisations about the magnitude of an effect throughout the entire domain or in areas of the domain that haven't been thoroughly studied.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Abbasnejad, S., & Norouzi, B. (2021). Biosynthesis of nano nickel oxide powder using *Malva sylvestris*; evaluation of electrocatalytic activity for determination of cephalexin in real samples. *Russian Journal of Electrochemistry*, 57(5), 478–489.
- [2] Adam, N. A., & Alarifi, G. (2021). Innovation practices for survival of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in the COVID-19 times: the role of external support. *Journal of innovation and entrepreneurship*, 10(1), 15.
- [3] Adula, M., & Kant, S. (2022). Interpretative Phenomenological Perceptual Study of Women Entrepreneurs Facing Challenges in Entrepreneurial Activity in the Horn of Africa. *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management, and Innovation*, 4(2), 321–335.
- [4] Alraja, M. N., Imran, R., Khashab, B. M., & Shah, M. (2022). Technological innovation, sustainable green practices and SMEs sustainable performance in times of crisis (COVID-19 pandemic). *Information Systems Frontiers*, 1–25.
- [5] Ayinaddis, S. G. (2022). The Relationship Between Service Innovation, Customer Satisfaction, and Loyalty Intention in Emerging Economies: An Evidence from Ethio Telecom. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 1–19.
- [6] Bansal, V., & Kant, S. (2018). Correlation between Entrepreneurialism, Nurturing the Spirit of Innovation and Sustainable Development Research on African Countries. *International Journal on Recent Trends in Business and Tourism (IJRTBT)*, 2(1), 23–26.
- [7] Cuevas-Vargas, H., Fernandez-Escobedo, R., Cortes-Palacios, H. A., & Ramirez-Lemus, L. (2021). The relation between adoption of information and communication technologies and marketing innovation as a key strategy to improve business performance. *Journal of Competitiveness*, 13(2), 23.
- [8] Daksa, M. D., Yismaw, M. A., Lemessa, S. D., & Hundie, S. K. (2018). Enterprise innovation in developing countries: an evidence from Ethiopia. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 7(1), 1–19.
- [9] GALLEGOS, J. F. D. C., & Miralles, F. (2020). Analyzing marketing innovation in Peruvian manufacturing companies of lower technological intensity. *Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 60, 195–207.

- [10] Gobena, A. E., & Kant, S. (2022). Assessing the Effect of Endogenous Culture, Local Resources, Eco-Friendly Environment and Modern Strategy Development on Entrepreneurial Development. *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management, and Innovation*, 4(1), 118-135.
- [11] Jaskyte, K. (2020). Technological and organizational innovations and financial performance: Evidence from nonprofit human service organizations. *VOLUNTAS: International Journal of Voluntary and Nonprofit Organizations*, 31(1), 142-152.
- [12] Kassa, E. T., & Getnet Mirete, T. (2022). Exploring factors that determine the innovation of micro and small enterprises: the role of entrepreneurial attitude towards innovation in Woldia, Ethiopia. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 11(1), 1-16.
- [13] Kiende, C. K., Mukulu, E., & Odhiambo, R. (2019). Influence of organization innovation on the performance of small and medium women-owned enterprises in Kenya. *Journal of Entrepreneurship & Project Management*, 3(1), 33-49.
- [14] Makanyeza, C., Mabenge, B. K., & Ngorora-Madzimure, G. P. K. (2023). Factors influencing small and medium enterprises' innovativeness: Evidence from manufacturing companies in Harare, Zimbabwe. *Global Business and Organizational Excellence*, 42(3), 10-23.
- [15] Moreira, A., Navaia, E., & Ribau, C. (2022). Moderation Effects of Government Institutional Support, Active and Reactive Internationalization Behavior on Innovation Capability and Export Performance. *Economies*, 10(8), 177.
- [16] Otache, I., & Usang, O. U. E. (2022). Innovation capability and SME performance in times of economic crisis: does government support moderate?. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 13(1), 76-88.
- [17] Peng, H., Shen, N., Ying, H., & Wang, Q. (2021). Can environmental regulation directly promote green innovation behavior?—based on situation of industrial agglomeration. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 314, 128044.
- [18] Sinaga, R. R. F., & Pustika, R. (2021). Exploring STUDENTS' ATTITUDE towards English online learning using moodle during COVID-19 pandemic at smk yadika bandarlampung. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Learning*, 2(1), 8-15.
- [19] Talegeta, S. (2014). Innovation and barriers to innovation: small and medium enterprises in Addis Ababa. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Development*, 2(1), 83-106.
- [20] Wakjira, G. G., & Kant, S. (2022). Significance Of Market Orientation On Business Performance With Mediating Role of Employee And Customer Satisfaction In Ethiopia Banks. *Partners Universal International Research Journal*, 1(4), 118-125.
- [21] YuSheng, K., & Ibrahim, M. (2020). Innovation capabilities, innovation types, and firm performance: evidence from the banking sector of Ghana. *Sage Open*, 10(2), 2158244020920892.
- [22] Zameer, H., Wang, Y., Vasbieva, D. G., & Abbas, Q. (2021). Exploring a pathway to carbon neutrality via reinforcing environmental performance through green process innovation, environmental orientation and green competitive advantage. *Journal of environmental management*, 296, 113383.
- [23] Muharam, H., Andria, F., & Tosida, E. T. (2020). Effect of process innovation and market innovation on financial performance with moderating role of disruptive technology. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11(1), 223-232.
- [24] Udriyah, U., Tham, J., & Azam, S. (2019). The effects of market orientation and innovation on competitive advantage and business performance of textile SMEs. *Management Science Letters*, 9(9), 1419-1428.